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A Brief Policy Memo on Strategies to Address Increasing Costs and Lagging in the US

I. Scoping the problem

Out-of-pocket medical expenses can lead to financial strain and even medical bankruptcy.

According to a 2022 survey, the excessive expense of health care has resulted in a world where 56% of Americans have some medical debt, with one in four owing \$10,000 or more, and emergency rooms are adding to it. In addition, 46% of those with medical debt are postponing home purchases, and 14% want to file for bankruptcy. Most persons with medical debt incurred it due to their health-care costs, with 29% including payments for dependents. 32% of individuals with medical debt believe they will be unable to pay off their medical debts in their lifetime. ¹

Every year, 530,000 American families file for bankruptcy due to medical bills. In addition, U.S. medical bills and indebtedness are responsible for 66.5% of all American personal insolvencies. ²

Graph showing per capita out-of-pocket expenditure in the US,1970-2020

¹ MedicalEconomics, webpage

² Konish -CNBC, webpage

Several factors contribute to the problem of medical bankruptcy and out-of-pocket expenses, including:

- Increased healthcare costs have been rising at a significantly higher pace than earnings and inflation, leaving many individuals unable to afford even primary medical care.²
- Lack of proper healthcare coverage forces many working Americans to pay a hefty chunk of their medical expenditures out-of-pocket because their deductibles, copays, and out-of-pocket maximums are so high.
- Lack of access to care leads people to put off or forgo needed medical treatment, leading to more severe health consequences and higher medical costs in the long run.⁴
- Inability to afford medical expenses due to unexpected medical emergencies or illnesses.⁴

Therefore, addressing the problem of out-of-pocket and medical bankruptcy will require a good health policy that includes:

- Addressing healthcare expenses with measures to minimize the total cost of healthcare, such as negotiating prescription prices and cutting administrative costs, may help lessen the financial load on patients.
- Expanding insurance coverage via governmental programs such as Medicaid and Medicare may assist in guaranteeing that people have access to critical medical care.
- Improving transparency around healthcare pricing and quality can help patients make informed decisions about their care and avoid unexpected costs.
- Providing financial assistance to low-income individuals and their families can offset the cost of medical care and reduce the risk of bankruptcy.⁵
- Advancing home-based care with improvements in internet, video, and remote monitoring capabilities.⁶

² Konish -CNBC, webpage

³ Commonwealth Fund. <https://doi.org/10.26099/x0cx-cp48>

⁴ KFF/NY Times survey 2016, page 16

⁵ Peterson-KFF Health System Tracker.-webpage

⁶ Shrank, Health Affairs-webpage

- Developing a high-value workforce. A coordinated strategy to train, deploy, and support a diverse health care workforce is essential for access, quality, and value, particularly in underresourced communities.⁶

II. Anchoring

Framework: Cancer patients/Healthcare as human right

Out-of-pocket expenses can significantly impact cancer patients and their families, both in terms of their financial well-being and ability to access necessary medical care.

Cancer is one of the most expensive diseases to treat in the US, and cancer-related expenses are rising due to an aging populace, access to treatment, innovation, and overutilization. However, innovative treatments come at a cost. Many insurance plans offer high deductibles, copays, and out-of-pocket maximums, leaving patients with very high medical bills they cannot afford and preventing them from getting primary medical care.⁷

Some of the ways out-of-pocket expenses can impact cancer patients include:

- Delayed treatment because of cost can worsen health care and lead to worse outcomes.

TABLE 4. THOSE WITH MEDICAL BILL PROBLEMS MORE LIKELY TO REPORT SKIPPING OR DELAYING CARE

Percent who say they or another family member living in their household have done each of the following in the past 12 months because of the COST:	Total		Insured		Uninsured	
	Medical bill problems	No medical bill problems	Medical bill problems	No medical bill problems	Medical bill problems	No medical bill problems
Put off/postponed getting dental care/check-ups	65%	31%	62%	29%	72%	42%
Relied on home remedies/over the counter drugs instead of going to see a doctor	62	32	58	30	71	44
Put off/postponed getting health care you needed	60	22	58	21	65	37
Not filled a prescription for medicine	43	14	41	14	45	13
Not gotten a medical test/treatment that was recommended by a doctor	43	13	43	13	43	13
Chosen a less expensive treatment than the one your doctor recommended	40	15	38	14	47	26
Cut pills in half/skipped doses of medicine	34	9	32	9	39	13
Skipped/postponed rehabilitation care that your doctor recommended	22	5	20	5	28	6

KFF Survey showing the impact of out-of-pocket expenses on medical care.⁴

⁴ KFF/NY Times survey 2016, page 16

⁶ Shrank, Health Affairs-webpage

⁷ Zafar, webpage

- Decreased medical compliance leading to the effectiveness of ongoing treatment.
- unaffordability of basic needs such as food, transportation, and housing due to financial strain.
- Mental health issues such as depression, anxiety, and suicide.

Cancer patients and caregivers spend 16%-42% of their annual income on out-of-pocket expenses. Healthcare systems have an opportunity to improve coverage of medical and non-medical costs for cancer patients to help alleviate this burden and ensure equitable access to care.⁸

Access to healthcare is a human right.⁹ WHO believes that Universal health care coverage is the perfect solution for out-of-pocket expenses by ensuring that each individual can access necessary medical care without worrying about financial hardship.

Protecting people from the financial consequences of paying for health services out of their own pockets reduces the risk of poverty due to unexpected illness, destroying their futures and those of their children.¹⁰

By providing universal access to healthcare, patients will receive preventive care, adhere to medical/surgical treatment, and stay healthy without thinking of all the consequences caused by deductibles, copays leading to high out-of-pocket expenses, and eventually medical bankruptcy.

When individuals are healthy, they are more likely to stay away from complex medical interventions down the road.

III. Potential Impact

In proposing the health policies following populations will benefit the most from the reduction or elimination of out-of-pocket expenses:

- Patients with chronic medical conditions such as cardiovascular disease (the leading cause of morbidity and mortality in the United States). This population will easily access preventive care, stay healthy, live longer, and avoid the burden caused by high out-of-pocket expenses.

⁸ Iraborri-PubMed-webpage

⁹ EPH538 class/discussion, January 24th 2023

¹⁰ WHO 2022-webpage

- Geriatric patients. This population has minimal financial resources requiring more routine medical care than young individuals. ¹¹

- Low-income individuals and families. This population struggles to afford healthcare and faces the negative consequences of copays, high deductibles, and out-of-pocket maximums.

- Rural residents. Besides the challenges of provider shortage, they also encounter barriers to healthcare access. This population must have enough financial means to pay for services, such as health or dental insurance, that the provider accepts. Also, high transportation costs to access specialized medical facilities make this population vulnerable to high out-of-pocket expenses. ¹²

- Individuals living with disabilities. This population requires regular and specialized medical care, yet they have minimal income and financial freedom.

Health policy that decreases or eliminates out-of-pocket will benefit a wide range of vulnerable populations. By implementing such policies, individuals will have access to primary and necessary healthcare, regardless of their health status and income.

IV. Potential Challenges

Implementing new health policy could be challenging because it involves changing the current healthcare system and more administrative work.

Reducing OOP expenses will increase healthcare spending due to an increased demand for medical services. ¹³

However, funding healthcare costs would be difficult in today's economy, and there will be political opposition in US Congress due to high government spending. In addition, some interest groups such as pharmaceutical and insurance companies will oppose any policy interfering with their profits.

In order to overcome these obstacles and prevent their harmful effects on individuals and families, the following strategies should be taken into consideration:

¹¹ ncbi-webpage

¹² Rural Health Information Hub-webpage

¹³ Commonwealth Fund-webpage

- Getting support from stakeholders
- Designing a cost-effective policy
- Addressing concerns from interest groups such as insurance and pharmaceutical companies,
- gradually bringing in changes without impacting the current healthcare system or increasing more administrative work.

By alleviating these challenges and successfully implementing a new health policy to reduce OOP expenses, individuals will have access to healthcare without fear of getting into poverty, debt, or medical bankruptcy.